

PREFACE

ISPRS Annals, Volume III, Part B5

Fabio Remondino, President, ISPRS Technical Commission V
FBK Trento, 3D Optical Metrology
via Sommarive 18, 38123 Trento, Italy

Commission V

Technical Commission V deals with with close-range imaging sensors and applications in the field of industrial metrology, cultural heritage, architecture, biomedical and geosciences. Close-range photogrammetry employs consumer grade and professional SLR cameras as well as active sensors like terrestrial laser scanners, RGBD cameras, gaming or stripe projection sensors. All these devices are investigated, combined and used for 3D representations and analyses of static and dynamic objects or scenes. Systems and algorithms for real-time imaging, mobile mapping applications and 3D modelling issues are also developed.

Following these challenges and research needs, the papers published in this volume depicts the latest developments in methodological aspects and the most interesting applications in terrestrial photogrammetry.

The papers in vision metrology showed new progresses in sensor modelling with interesting applications in the industry sector. Cultural Heritage attracted many submissions with various worldwide applications which depicted how 3D recording sensors are more and more used and important for detailed documentation, conservation, preservation and valorisation needs. Various contributions refer to the characterization, integration and performance analyses of terrestrial sensors. 3D modelling and BIM are still very active whereas geosciences and bio-medical contributions demonstrated the replicability, reliability and added value of 3D sensors and methods.

The Volume related to TC V contains 25 Full Papers accepted on the base of double blind review from originally submitted 42 full papers.

I believe these volumes nicely recap the state of the art, current trends and possible applications in close-range photogrammetry. On behalf of Technical Commission V, I would like to thank the local organisers in Prague, the members of the international program committee, all Working Group officers and all reviewers for their hard organizational work and efforts in the paper reviewing process.